

Optimizing urban permeability: a GIS-based site selection approach for permeable pavements: a case study of Santander, Spain.

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Highlights

- Innovative GIS approach for efficient permeable pavement site selection in urban areas.
- Enhanced urban water management through strategic placement of permeable surfaces.
- Significant reduction in runoff and flood risks via GIS-based planning.

Introduction

As cities worldwide grapple with accelerated urbanization, the imperative to address water management issues has never been more urgent. The relentless expansion of urban landscapes, accompanied by the extensive impermeabilization of surfaces, has brought an increase in surface runoff (Santos et al., 2021). This phenomenon not only exacerbates the risk of urban flooding but also poses severe threats to the integrity of water quality. Against this backdrop, it is essential to explore and implement innovative and sustainable urban stormwater management strategies (Zhang, 2016).

Permeable pavements emerged within nature-based solutions as part of this repertoire of solutions with different typologies and designs (Santos et al., 2021). As a general rule for this kind of infrastructure, they allow rainwater to percolate through the surface, mitigating runoff, aiding groundwater recharge and improving overall urban water quality. However, the deployment of permeable pavements in urban environments is not without complexities. It requires a methodical and strategic approach, particularly in the identification and selection of the most favourable sites for installation.

Hence, Geographic Information Systems (GIS) are important for providing a comprehensive and spatially detailed analysis of urban attributes (Barboza et al., 2022), which enables the precise determination of suitable locations for permeable pavements. This research explores the use of GIS for urban site selection, taking into account a diverse portfolio of variables including potential zones and existing urban infrastructure. By embedding these variables in a GIS framework, this study aims to improve the permeability of urban surfaces by facilitating decision-making processes, thereby promoting a more sustainable approach to water management throughout the city.

Methodology

Despite their significant environmental benefits in terms of water management, permeable pavements typically face disadvantages in terms of resistance and durability compared to their non-permeable counterparts (Thorpe & Zhuge, 2010). Furthermore, the application of permeable pavements is generally constrained to areas with slopes less than 3% (Woods-Ballard et al., 2007), limiting their widespread deployment in diverse urban topographies. This limitation is particularly pronounced in road areas, where permeable asphalt is more susceptible to abrasion and damage from heavy vehicle traffic. However, it is important to note that permeable pavements also possess advantageous properties for urban environments, such as reduced noise pollution due to lower tire noise.

Based on these considerations, the study was initiated with the strategic acquisition of several freely available datasets. Data acquisition was guided according to the flowchart in Figure 1, ensuring systematic consideration of urban elements that could influence the durability of permeable pavements. Specifically, areas with frequent heavy vehicle traffic or high friction were excluded from potential sites, while parking lots, parks, gardens, and other recreational zones were evaluated for their suitability.

Table 1 presents the detailed data used in the methodology, including the conditional factors and urban elements considered, as well as the types of data processed. Special attention was paid to the application of buffers and intersection geometries to accurately represent the interaction of various urban elements with roadway areas. Constraining factors such as street crossings, bus stops, loading zones, stop signs, pedestrian crossings and tunnels were processed to identify areas where the implementation of permeable pavements would be less effective or not recommended. This approach, based on geospatial analysis and data, provided the basis for identifying the most suitable locations for the implementation of permeable pavements, taking into account both their environmental benefits and practical urban constraints.

Figure 1. Workflow diagram showing the city elements considered and their respective processing.

Table 1. Data used in the methodology.

Conditional	Urban elements	Data Type	Processing
Potential Zone	Roads and associated zones	Polygonal SHP	None
	Parking	Polygonal SHP	None
	Parks, Gardens & Recreational Zones	Polygonal SHP	Merge
	Park paths and hiking trails	Line SHP	Buffer 3m
	Cycle paths	Line SHP	Buffer 3m
Restrictive factor	Street crosses	Line SHP	Intersect & Buffer 10m
	Bus stops	JSON point	Georeferenced & Buffer 10m
	Load zones	JSON point	Georeferenced & Buffer 10m
	Stop signals	Point SHP	Buffer 5m
	Pedestrian crossings	Point SHP	Buffer 10m
	Tunnels	Line SHP	Selection by zone
	Slope	Raster	Conditional <3%

Results and discussion

The GIS-based analysis revealed a map with the optimal placement of permeable pavements within urban environments (Figure 2). By integrating multiple datasets, key locations were identified that not only met the criteria for permeable pavement installation but also were in line with practical constraints. These findings underscore the complexity of urban infrastructure planning, where environmental goals must be balanced with practical urban development limitations.

The GIS-based analysis produced a description of the city's potential for the integration of permeable pavements, with a total area of 298.7 km². The "road potential zone" appears as the most prominent candidate, with 29.90% of the total potential area. This substantial part highlights the transforming capacity of the main roads in urban stormwater management areas. It is followed by the "private no building zone", with 15.14% of the total potential. In a similar vein, "urban green spaces" represent 12.60% of the potential area, suggesting that the city's parks and green spaces can be vital components of our sustainable urban infrastructure as well as recreational assets.

"Parking" represents 12.45% of the potential area, which points to the feasibility of converting expansive and impervious surfaces into permeable land, thereby reducing the ecological impact of vehicle storage spaces. "Land associated with road networks" has 11.85%, underlining the importance of integrating sustainable practices into the connective fabric of our urban environment. Other more modest, yet crucial, contributions come from "Recreational areas" and "Unused areas", with 8.29% and 5.38%, respectively. These outcomes illustrate the potential for improving community spaces and activating underutilized areas with environmental solutions in line with public use and enjoyment.

Figure 2. Map detail representing the potential zones for the implementation of porous pavements in the city of Santander.

Conclusions and future work

Overall, the GIS-based approach employed in this study proved to be an effective tool for identifying potential sites for the installation of permeable pavements. This method provides a data-driven avenue for urban planners and policy makers to improve urban sustainability. The results of the study provide valuable information for informed decision-making on the integration of permeable pavements in urban areas. One of the possible lines of research to be pursued after this preliminary study would be to cross-reference flood risk maps to prioritize those areas of the city with the highest risk. It could also be possible to use this methodology for other nature-based solutions or also to deepen in which type of permeable pavement would be more suitable for each urban element.

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